

Piezoelectric accelerometer designs for totally implantable auditory prostheses

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Abstract. The goal of this work is to develop a totally implantable sensor utilizing microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) technology for totally implantable auditory prosthesis applications. Totally implantable auditory prostheses cannot exist without a sensor capable of replacing the current external microphones in hearing aids and cochlear implants. Present-day implantable sensors do not meet the design specifications, acoustic performance, or size requirements for implantable prostheses. However, our work has shown that piezoelectric MEMS accelerometers in dual- and multi-bandwidth designs can meet these requirements.

INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization [1] projects that by 2050, 2.5 billion people will have some degree of hearing loss, and at least 1 in 10 will have disabling hearing loss. Hearing loss is defined into four categories: mild, moderate, severe, and profound, and may affect one or both ears. Unaddressed hearing loss can impact many aspects of life, including communication and speech [2], cognition [3], social isolation [4], loneliness [1], stigma [2], and dementia [5]. Moreover, adults with hearing loss have a higher unemployment rate than the general population [1].

Depending on the severity and damage, hearing aids (HAs) and cochlear implants (CIs) are intervention options that help people treat their hearing loss [2]. HAs help improve hearing and speech comprehension by amplifying sound vibrations entering the ear [6], and CIs utilize an electrode array to directly stimulate the auditory nerve [7]. Despite the benefits associated with HAs and CIs, including improved quality of life [8], users continue to feel self-conscious and uncomfortable due to the visible device components and experience financial burden due to the ongoing maintenance costs [9]. Eliminating the external components from these devices, i.e., their external microphones, may help ameliorate these issues. However, an implantable device must meet the stringent technical specifications for an auditory prosthesis and be robust.

A totally implantable auditory prosthesis (TIAP) could replace HA and CI microphones by utilizing a miniaturized sensor. The sensor would be implanted within the ear and out of sight. The biggest challenge that remains in commercializing a TIAP is the development of such a sensor that is capable of matching or exceeding the capabilities of current external microphones [10]. In this paper, we present a brief overview of our work in designing a sensor capable of a TIAP application.

Our studies have indicated that piezoelectric microelectromechanical systems (MEMS) accelerometers have the potential to function as implantable sensors within the middle ear and meet a low-noise floor over a 100 Hz – 8 kHz frequency range in a small form factor. Our devices utilize proof-mass-loaded piezoelectric cantilever bimorph (two-layer) plates that convert mechanical vibrations to electrical signals. We have developed an analytical model [11] that has been experimentally validated [12] and is used to optimize our designs. With our analytical model, we showed that a small low-noise 20-phon design can be met with a dual-bandwidth sensor [13]. The dual-bandwidth design uses two piezoelectric cantilever bimorph plates, each operating at different frequency intervals within 100 Hz - 8 kHz. Our current investigation aims to identify the optimal number of piezoelectric cantilever bimorph plates (sensing elements) in multi-bandwidth designs that further minimize the size of the overall MEMS design while maintaining low-noise performance.

METHODS

Analytical Model and Sensor Design

Fig. 1 shows the side-view layout of one piezoelectric cantilever bimorph plate placed on top of a printed circuit board (PCB). The analytical model used in this work to guide the design optimization of multi-bandwidth sensors was first presented in Hake [11] and was experimentally validated in Hake et al. [12]. The multi-bandwidth designs are comprised of multiple piezoelectric cantilever bimorph plates (sensing elements) tip-loaded by silicon proof masses that produce measurable voltage outputs (V_{out}) when deflected. The piezoelectric plate's three electrodes, which are placed on the top, in the middle, and on the bottom, connect to the necessary electronics to extract V_{out} . The piezoelectric material selected is aluminum nitride (AlN) due to its low dielectric losses that aid in maintaining low noise. The variables associated with the sensor's dimensions are labeled in the figure. Biocompatible packaging (titanium) will be used to house the sensor.

Although the structure can be subjected to either transverse displacement (W_{bz}), longitudinal displacement (U_{bx}), rotation (θ_{by}), or a combination of all, only the transverse (W_{bz}) excitation is considered in this initial investigation. Lastly, the sensitivity of the sensor can be calculated using V_{out} normalized to the base acceleration excitation as follows: $V_{out}/\omega^2 W_{bz}$ with units $V/(m/s^2)$, where $\omega = 2\pi f$ is the radian frequency, and f is the frequency of vibration.

FIGURE 1. Side view of one piezoelectric cantilever bimorph plate made out of aluminum nitride (AlN) sitting on top of a printed circuit board (PCB) and connected to necessary electronics to extract the voltage output (V_{out}). Three electrodes are deposited on the top, middle, and bottom of the plate. Each plate has dimensions of length L_b , total thickness t_b , and width b . The proof mass sits flush against the edge of the plate and has length L_M , thickness t_M , width b , mass M , and moment of inertia I_M . W_{bz} is defined as the prescribed base displacement in the z -direction, U_{bx} is defined as the prescribed based displacement in the x -direction, and θ_{by} is defined as the prescribed base rotation about the y -axis. Packaging is not shown. Not to scale.

Minimum Detectable Acceleration

To determine the optimal number of sensing elements when designing multi-bandwidth sensors, we use the assumed-mode beam deflection equation (details are provided in Hake [11] and Hake et al. [13]). This equation allows us to derive a closed-form expression for the minimum detectable acceleration that each sensing element can detect subjected to W_{bz} as

$$MDA_z = \sqrt{\frac{8k_B T}{9}} \underbrace{\frac{1}{\sqrt{\omega}}}_{\text{Frequency}} \underbrace{\frac{(2d_{31}^2 - 4\epsilon_{33}s_{11})\sqrt{\tan \delta}}{d_{31}s_{11}\rho_M\sqrt{\epsilon_{33}}}}_{\text{Material properties}} \times \underbrace{\frac{\sqrt{t_{piezo}^3}}{L_M t_M \sqrt{bL(L+L_M)}}}_{\text{Sensing plate and proof mass dimensions}} \quad (1)$$

where k_B is the Boltzmann constant, T is the temperature in Kelvin, ρ_M is the proof mass density, $\tan(\delta)$ is the loss tangent of the piezoelectric material (AlN), d_{31} is the piezoelectric coefficient, s_{11} is the material's elastic compliance

measured under a constant electric field, t_{piezo} is the thickness of one piezoelectric layer i.e., half of t_b , and ϵ_{33} is the relative permittivity measured under zero strain and calculated for the plane-strain constitutive relationship as $\epsilon_{33} = \epsilon_{33}^T - d_{31}^2/s_{11}$ where ϵ_{33}^T is the permittivity measured under constant stress. The MDA_z represents the lowest bound of the sensor noise as additional noise will be introduced to the overall system through the amplifier circuits.

Design Specifications

The specifications that constrain the design of multi-bandwidth sensors include the noise, size, weight, and frequency bandwidth. The noise of the sensor must be low and close to the normal hearing threshold. Thus, we select the 20-phon noise floor [14] as the initial target for these designs as it encompasses almost the entire conversational speech range [15]. To ensure that the sensor can detect 20-phon, the MDA_z of that sensor must detect ossicular accelerations equivalent to 20-phon. These 20-phon acceleration values are determined by mapping umbo acceleration data from Sachse et al. [16] and Goode et al. [17] to 20-phon acceleration data (more details in Hake et al. [13]). The size of the sensor must also remain small to fit in the middle ear [18] and lightweight to reduce the mass loading on the ossicles. From our preliminary cadaveric temporal bone testing with a commercially available voice accelerometer (Vesper Technologies Inc., VA1200), we determined that the size of $2\text{ mm} \times 2\text{ mm} \times 1\text{ mm}$ is a good initial target for the umbo [19]. Lastly, the frequency range operation of the sensor is selected as 100 Hz - 8 kHz to match the performance of current commercial HAs and CIs [20].

Dual-Bandwidth Designs

Single-bandwidth accelerometers are not able to meet the performance needed for a TIAP application, as was shown in Hake et al. [12]. However, the dual-bandwidth sensor presented in Hake et al. [13] was able to meet the 20-phon noise floor, maintain a small size, and operate from 100 Hz - 8 kHz. This sensor used two sensing elements, each operating at different sub-bandwidths that together add to cover the desired total frequency range. Fig. 2 shows the top view of a dual-bandwidth sensor with its two sensing elements (1 and 2). It also shows the corresponding sensitivity response of each sensing element, along with the designated frequency operations. This dual-bandwidth design employs the use of a transition or cross-over frequency. This is the frequency at which the operation of sensing element 1 stops and the operation of sensing element 2 begins. Specifically, in the dual-bandwidth design from Hake et al. [13], the first sensing element operated from 100 Hz to 1.25 kHz, and the second sensing element operated from 1.25 kHz to 8 kHz. The 1.25 kHz was the cross-over frequency. It is important to note that in addition to the necessary electronics needed to extract V_{out} from each sensing element, further filtering is needed to manage the transition between sensing elements, and amplification is needed to equalize the sensitivities throughout the total frequency range.

FIGURE 2. Dual-bandwidth sensor top view diagram and its sensitivity response curves. The top view of the sensor shows its two sensing elements (1 and 2), and the sensitivity response curves are evaluated for the frequency range 100 Hz - 8 kHz. The transition frequency and frequency operation of each sensing element are labeled.

Multi-Bandwidth Designs

Multi-bandwidth designs operate similarly to the dual-bandwidth design presented in the previous section, with the only difference that more sensing elements are added, and thus, more transition or cross-over frequencies are included. Fig. 3 shows a multi-bandwidth configuration with four cantilever bimorph plates arranged in one device. Once again, each sensing element operates over a sub-bandwidth within 100 Hz - 8 kHz.

FIGURE 3. Example of a multi-bandwidth design with four sensing elements.

The design optimization process involves a combinatorial analysis that is more complex for multi-bandwidth designs than for the dual-bandwidth. Specifically, the optimization includes investigating combinations of cross-over frequencies for each sensing element and evaluating its dimensions (t_M , L_M , L , and b) so that the sensor meets the 20-phon noise floor. The optimization then outputs the design with the smallest sensor surface area. With a higher number of sensing elements in a multi-bandwidth design, the process becomes more complex as the model needs to balance minimizing the surface area and ensuring that the sensing elements' cross-over frequencies overlap to ensure a continuous operation. For instance, sensing element 1 must share the same cross-over frequency with sensing element 2 to ensure continuous frequency coverage.

With our design investigation, we have identified that multi-bandwidth designs are smaller than the dual-bandwidth design presented in Hake et al. [13] and can meet and match its performance, meeting the 20-phon noise floor and frequency bandwidth operation.

DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSIONS

In this paper, we provided a concise overview of piezoelectric cantilever bimorph accelerometer designs for totally implantable auditory prostheses. Our sensor design was constrained and guided by the design specifications of low-noise, compact and small size, and total frequency range of operation. Hake et al. [13] proposed a new dual-bandwidth design capable of meeting the specified criteria and utilized two piezoelectric cantilever bimorph plates, each operating at smaller frequency ranges. With further investigation, we find that multi-bandwidth designs can also meet the same design specifications but at even smaller form factors.

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COMMENTS AND DISCUSSION

[Elizabeth, Olson]: Why not just use sensing element 1 and then do some filtering (like with a notch filter) to get rid of the resonance peak since it looked like the sensitivity of that sensing element was always high?

[Panagiota, Kitsopoulos]: Filtering is an option, but it would increase the complexity of the design. In Fig. 2, we see that sensing element 1 has constant sensitivity until the cross-over frequency and then experiences resonance, after which the sensitivity is not constant. A filtering approach would need to ensure that the resonance peak of sensing element 1 is smoothed out and that the entire sensitivity of that sensing element remains constant (does not increase more than 3 dB) for the entire frequency bandwidth of 100 Hz - 8 kHz. This filtering would also introduce phase shifts. However, your suggestion is really interesting as we could take advantage of the lower MDA over a broader bandwidth if these phase shifts do not adversely affect the perceptual experience of the user. Naturally, we would expect the influence of phase shifts to depend on the frequency band. Simple filtering would not be sufficient to do this. Hence, to decrease complexity, we opt for two sensing elements where amplification of the sensing element 2 signal would be needed to equalize both sensitivities. Some simple filtering (band pass filters) would also be required to manage the transition between sensing element operation.

[Sunil, Puria]: Does the proof mass require the use of a Wheatstone bridge for motion detection?

[Panagiota, Kitsopoulos]: No, we do not need a Wheatstone bridge for the proof mass because we are using cantilever bimorph plates that are piezoelectric with electrodes intermixed to detect motion. The proof mass is made out of silicon and does not directly detect motion but does provide the inertial load that allows for a higher sensitivity.

[Stefan, Stenfelt]: What is the mass of this device, and how would that affect perception?

[Panagiota, Kitsopoulos]: The anticipated weight of the device is less than 15 mg, including the integrated circuitry, printed circuit board, and biocompatible packaging (titanium). More testing will be needed to understand the direct effect on the ossicular chain.

[Joshua, Hajicek]: For the dual- and multi-bandwidth designs, you mention that the sensing elements “stop” at the cross-over frequency. Are you suggesting that the response of, for example, “element 1” simply falls into the noise floor and hence doesn’t contribute to the perceptual output?

[Panagiota, Kitsopoulos]: All sensing elements within a design operate throughout the frequency range of 100 Hz - 8 kHz, but their operation is managed by simple filtering. For example, sensing element 1 shown in Fig. 2 would use a band pass filter between 100 Hz and the cross-over frequency.

[Joshua, Hajicek]: When moving from a single to a dual-sensor, and then to a multi-sensor design, we would expect the noise floor to increase with the number of sensors. In a 3-sensor design, is the noise floor still negligible?

[Panagiota, Kitsopoulos]: All sensors (single, dual, and multi) are designed to meet the same 20-phon noise floor over 100 Hz - 8 kHz.

[Emma, Wawrzynek]: What is the main benefit of the multi-bandwidth design, and are you concerned about the drop in sensitivity for each cantilever if you increase the number of them?

[Panagiota, Kitsopoulos]: The main benefit of multi-bandwidth designs is that they are smaller than previous designs but can still have the same performance (low noise over 100 Hz - 8 kHz). We are not concerned about the sensitivity drop because (as mentioned previously) we will be using amplification to equalize all sensitivities.